

Project Portfolio Management

By Edwin Amuga

Organizations worldwide are increasingly establishing project administrations and project management offices to support the success and sustain the benefits of projects in a bid to meet the objectives of shareholders and meet strategic goals of the business. Portfolio management as an approach aims to achieve the strategic goals by selecting, prioritizing, assessing and managing projects, programs and other works related based on how they are aligned and contribute to the strategies and objectives of the organization. A portfolio is a reflection of the investments made by the organization which are related to or aligned with the objectives and strategic goals of the organization (Fesenko and Fesenko, 2017). Through it, priorities are identified and decisions regarding investments are made and resources allocated to achieve the strategic goals and objectives. The organization is obliged to ask itself why the work is being undertaken if the components of the portfolio, such as programs, projects and other related works, are not aligned with the organizational strategies.

An organization's operational and project aspects have to be factored into the management of a portfolio. The middle triangle in the portfolio management framework above establishes the distinct initiatives needed to achieve the targets of performance of the organization. The ongoing project management and authorized programs and projects correspond with executing the operational, project, and program activities to realize the performance targets.

Portfolio management ensures that chosen and completed projects meet the organization's goals. The portfolio manager looks for means to improve return on investments with a keen focus on the value of the portfolio and the change in the portfolio's value since the last reporting. The organization has to install a project management office or designate someone to perform the roles of the portfolio management process (Doronina and Doronina, 2018). This is in a bid to determine the viable project mix to meet organizations strategic goals, balance portfolio to ensure project mix balancing the long term and short term, risks and rewards, research and

development as well as project and operations. The roles of the project management office or designate will also include chosen project monitoring, planning, and execution, analyzing the portfolio's performance to improve it, evaluating new opportunities against the portfolio, and availing information and recommendations to decision-makers.

The organization must also find ways to bridge the gap between strategic planning and implementation of the projects. This has to be done by identifying missing links causing the gaps and consequently slowing down the implementation and making the strategic direction dysfunctional (Burmistrov, Siniavina and Iliashenk, 2018). The organization makes the call execution-oriented paradigm call when there is an integration gap between the strategic planning and the implementation process. Closing this gap remains vital to achieving and sustaining a competitive advantage. In many organizations, there are usually a range of integrative links missing between the strategic plan and the strategic implementation including, focus on strategic implementation, understating the common top-down, organizational focal point on responsibility delegation to functional VPs, executive transitional problems, and feedback loop.

Project management model

There are a few models for project management in an organization. The project management office provides a project excellence center overseeing the execution and control of projects where discipline is lacking. In the case of complex problems, the project management office looks into many ways and perspectives and reallocates resources as needed, and the project manager remains focused on the benefits. The project management office also aims to advise on investment opportunities and the achievement of strategic goals when there is a resource limitation problem.

The function spectrum of the project management office includes two major categories, namely, team-focused functions and enterprise-oriented functions. Team focused functions are where the enterprise Project management office management projects for the project management team whereas the enterprise-oriented functions is where the enterprise project management office methodically and efficiently helps the project management teams handle the work by themselves.

Portfolio management implementation takes time as all its aspects are numerous. The implementation takes more than a year and however, an organization should try and implement as many aspects as possible in the first year and strive to complete it the following year (Daniel and Daniel, 2018). This should be done with the reason for the implementation of project portfolio management in mind. The application of the PortMON framework helps when the question is not adequately addressed.

The PortMON framework

The requirements from the customer are gathered and the expected results drawn out to inform the implementation of the portfolio management, the organization is ready operationally and from the projects perspective. There have to be such factors and assets as enterprise

environmental factors and organizational process assets to assess the organizational operational readiness. The assets and factors are recognized by using an assessment tool that focuses on finance, marketing, human resource and information technology. The readiness of the organization on the projects viewpoint is done by ensuring the presence of some practices to the achievement of goals (Zuo, Zhao, Nguyen, Ma and Gao, 2018). The best practices in assessed by recognizing the Organizational Project Management Maturity Model.

With the results of organization readiness to introduction and implementation of portfolio management, it is imperative that a number of minimums are met. The traditional approach to the establishment of the project portfolio management office should be followed when there is lack of Best Practices, Enterprise Environmental Factors and Organizational Process Assets (Galli, 2018). There is a need to build the missing Best Practices, Enterprise Environmental Factors, and Organizational Process Assets to be in a position to adapt to the framework. The organization should start adapting to the PortMON framework (Oslo and Wu, 2015). The framework processes include adapting to decision analysis, determining the most important goals, the assessment of the OP asset and EE factors, assessing best practices, findings mapping, building the missing Best Practices, Enterprise Environmental Factors, and Organizational Process Assets, establishing the Portfolio project management office to adapt to the approach (Kivila, Martinsuo, and Vuorinen, 2017).

The desire to create a formalized portfolio management function will match the desire to efficiently and effectively manage the programs, operations and projects (Padalkar and Gopinath, 2016). The two main functions need Project portfolio management office assistance, facilitation and guidance. An organization needs Project management office team-focused function groups in response to the rapid nature of the PortMON framework (San Cristobal, 2017). On the other

hand, organizations on maturity path have a range of forms of enterprise-oriented function groups on top of the team focused functions.

Portfolio management process

Portfolio management process identifies crucial differentiates such as the return on investment, efficiency, risks and strategic alignment and uses them, to select high impact projects, clear clutter and set priorities. Discipline takes center stage during tradeoffs.

Companies train their project management personnel on the method to improve project results. Multiple unforeseen business factors could lead to delays and losses when a project manager or a contractor lacks sophisticated project control and monitoring tools (Whyte, 2019). The present case study incorporates several crucial project monitoring and controlling methods accessible for use by development project managers in such fields as construction.

An organization's primary objective is to make a fortune on project activities. Making a fortune depends on a good understanding of the project requirements a company intends to invest in. The usefulness of project management office is indicated by the ability of the information in

the smoothly run projects and ensuring value (Moustafa, 2015). Efficient projects spur a country's economic growth and development and expand markets to enhance private capital. Reliable project management practices and process is therefore crucial for company growth as investors need project viability information so as to make informed investment decisions. Project viability information strongly impacts the allocation of resources, and for this reason, project managers must adequately prepare and present the information to allow senior managers to make economic and investment decisions to reduce risk and capitalize on project value (Barreto and Ishimura, 2017). Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in their growth history attributable to crumbling investor interests in companies with volatile stock prices.

Project portfolio management accomplishes three objectives. These include aligning strategy and execution and eliminate pet projects, maximizing the entire portfolio value to get the most out of it and increase return on the investment and balance the portfolio to make it less risky and focused on both on term and short term results (Silvius, 2017). Organizations must combine good project management with effective project portfolio management to achieve gals such as higher productivity, less chaos, faster time to the market and implementation of organizational strategy.

References

- Barreto, A.M.M. and Ishimura, N., A determination formula on the copula-based estimation of Value at Risk for the portfolio problem.
- Olson, D. L., & Wu, D. D. (2015). *Enterprise risk management* (Vol. 3). World Scientific Publishing Company.
- Daniel, P. A., & Daniel, C. (2018). Complexity, uncertainty and mental models: From a paradigm of regulation to a paradigm of emergence in project management. *International journal of project management*, 36(1), 184-197.
- Galli, B. J. (2018). Project management maturity models: an overview of the common models and a proposed uniform model. *International Journal of Applied Logistics (IJAL)*, 8(2), 19-38.
- Whyte, J. (2019). How digital information transforms project delivery models. *Project management journal*, 50(2), 177-194.
- Mustafa, A. J. (2015). *Organizational Project Management Maturity Model (OPM3) to Improve Ministry of Construction and Housing (MOCAH) Within Kurdistan Regional Government* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Doronina, J., & Doronina, E. (2018). MODELS OF IT-PROJECT MANAGEMENT. *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Technol.*, 10(5).
- Fesenko, T., & Fesenko, G. (2017). Developing gender maturity models to project and programme management. *Eastern-European Journal of Interiorise Technologies.*, 85(1/3 (85), 46-55.

- Burmistrov, A., Siniavina, M., & Iliashenko, O. (2018). Project Management Life Cycle Models to Improve Management in High-rise Construction. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 33, p. 03005). EDP Sciences.
- San Cristóbal, J. R. (2017). Complexity in project management. *Procedia Computer Science*, 121, 762-766.
- Kivilä, J., Martinsuo, M., & Vuorinen, L. (2017). Sustainable project management through project control in infrastructure projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(6), 1167-1183.
- Silvius, G. (2017). Sustainability as a new school of thought in project management. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 166, 1479-1493.
- Zuo, J., Zhao, X., Nguyen, Q. B. M., Ma, T., & Gao, S. (2018). Soft skills of construction project management professionals and project success factors. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*.
- Padalkar, M., & Gopinath, S. (2016). Six decades of project management research: Thematic trends and future opportunities. *International Journal of Project Management*, 34(7), 1305-1321.